

SQUEEZE FLOW OF RANDOMLY-ORIENTED STRANDS THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Current applications of thermoplastic composites in aerospace structures are limited to simple components with minimal curvature and thickness variations. This limitation exists because continuous fibre (CF) thermoplastic composites, while exhibiting excellent mechanical performance, are difficult to form. The automotive industry can produce parts with intricate features made from flow moulding compounds, but their mechanical properties are generally too low for aerospace applications. A literature survey showed that preforms with long discontinuous fibres (LDF) and high fibre volume fractions (> 50 %) have the potential for being used in structural components due to their impressive forming and mechanical characteristics [1-5].

1.1 Randomly Oriented Strands (ROS)

Lying between these two extremes, randomly oriented strands of unidirectional prepreg composite tape (ROS), with high fibre volume fractions (>50%), have attractive forming and mechanical characteristics [1-6]. This paper focuses on the processing of ROS thermoplastic composites by compression moulding.

In this process, strands of thermoplastic composite tapes are positioned randomly in a mould cavity (see Figure 1). The setup is then compressed under a hot press to consolidate the material. Complex shapes including corners, thickness changes, ribs or holes can be obtained in one compression moulding step.

The material deformation behaviour is a crucial aspect of the press forming of randomly oriented strands, understanding this phenomenon will help to

determine the process window and predict the final part quality. The deformation mechanisms occurring during press forming of ROS are similar to those encountered in randomly distributed fibre bundles such as sheet moulding compound forming. We assume that the material has three different deformation modes:

1. An elastic compaction behaviour, denoted as *packing deformation*, at low load. It is mostly associated to the bending and conformation of the strands. Hereunder, we consider that normal stresses involved while press forming ROS is way higher than the packing stress. The packing deformation therefore occurs only at very low load during the initial stage of the process.
2. A *squeeze flow* at the macroscopic scale of the part. At this scale the material can be considered as an homogeneous medium that undergoes a squeeze flow imposed by the hot press. The viscous behaviour of the equivalent homogeneous material is intimately linked to the sliding between strands [7-10]. The macroscopic squeeze flow ensures that material will flow and fill intricate features. These areas, such as corners or ribs, may indeed remain empty after the initial operator positioning of the strands in the mould.
3. A flow at the mesoscopic scale of the strand. In this mode, the applied pressure results in a spreading of each strand. With this squeezing, the gaps between strands reduce. This mechanism is denoted as the *inter-strand void content* reduction. These inter-strand voids have to reduce enough to prevent crack initiation and dramatic strength property loss in the final part. It is a usual rule of thumb to guarantee a void content below 1% in aeronautic parts.

The present study aims at modelling and predicting the latter leading phenomenon in order to better understand its sensitivity to the process parameters (temperature, pressure, strand geometry...).

1.2 Macroscopic squeeze flow

In order to predict the forming of ROS composite parts, the macroscopic squeeze flow behaviour of a flat plate at forming temperatures must be studied. A constant volume and a constant pressure configurations were investigated. In the first one, the platens are larger than the sample, so the material volume stays constant throughout the experiment. In the second one, the platens are initially fully filled with material, so the contact pressure remains constant throughout the test. In both cases, the pre-consolidated samples were placed between the two platens and heated up to forming temperature (between 370-400°C). Once the target temperature was reached, either a constant load or a constant closure rate was applied. The load evolution and the change in sample height were measured over time.

In a previous study, the effect of the applied load on the evolution of the thickness with time was studied for ROS and UD samples [1]. In-plane flow was also measured and it was found that ROS underwent non-uniform flow that highly depended on strands configuration. Many authors studied squeeze flow of composites during forming processes using different material behaviours such as Newtonian or Carreau fluid [7-8]. But no extensive study on ROS material has been conducted to the best knowledge of the authors. So, there is an interest to characterize the behaviour of ROS material, more particularly the non-uniform flow front through *in-situ* measurements. This can be a challenging task as the forming temperature of this material is relatively high (370-400°C).

1.3 X-Ray tomography

X-Ray tomography is a non-destructive inspection technique that allows the study of the microstructure of materials. It has been used recently to measure the impregnation for an out-of-autoclave prepreg, in order to characterize the consolidation and void formation mechanisms [11-12]. Typically, to obtain relevant information from X-Ray tomography one needs a material with at least two phases of different density, which was the case for thermoset matrix

composites used by Centea *et al.*, but not for Carbon/PEEK composite. The density difference between carbon fibres and PEEK matrices is too small. So, in order to use X-ray tomography a different density material must be added to the fibres to act as markers.

1.4 Objective

In this paper a novel experimental approach is developed in order to characterize the non-uniform flow front of ROS Carbon/PEEK composites. Then, a squeeze flow model with an original visco-plastic behaviour is proposed. In section 2, the experimental methods are described. In section 3, a model for the squeeze flow behaviour of ROS is presented. In the last section, the experimental and modelling results obtained in this study are presented and discussed.

2 Experimental methods

The proposed method to track the squeeze flow behaviour of ROS samples consisted to apply a conductive silver paint on marker strands. These markers are then placed at strategic locations through the thickness of the part. The initial and final position of the markers can then accurately be measured using X-Ray tomography (Fig. 2). The markers can be used to extract relevant information on the flow profile and deformation mechanisms. They also help to identify consolidation defects such as compaction gradients and large fibre waviness.

2.1 Material

The material used in this study was a unidirectional Carbon / PEEK (PolyEtherEtherKetone) TC1200 tape with a fibre volume fraction of about 60% provided by Tencate. The squeeze flow experiments were performed using a 6.35 mm wide tape. An automated tape cutter (Kingsing Machinery Co. Limited, model KS-915) was used to cut the tape into 25.4 mm long strands. A conductive silver paint with 40% silver made by M.E. Taylor Engineering, Inc. was applied to strands used to track the flow front with X-Ray tomography.

2.2 Instrumented hot press

The manufacturer's recommended consolidation temperature was between 370 and 400°C. The compaction was applied in an instrumented hot press

(Figure 3). The fixture consisted of a custom built miniaturized heated press. The testing section consisted of two steel platens (100 mm x 100 mm) heated using four 500 W cartridge heaters. The platens' temperature was controlled by a DSS-15 auto-tuning PID controller from DME. A cooling system using compressed air was also used to cooldown the fixture quickly after each test. The cooling rate was adjusted by varying the air pressure. The apparatus was mounted into a 250 kN MTS testing machine used in compression. Either a constant closure rate or a constant load was applied. The sample thickness change was measured using a laser extensometer.

2.3 Test procedure

The procedure used to characterize the flow front involved a four step process, as shown in Figure 4. First, the samples were pre-consolidated. Second, the sample was scanned using X-Ray tomography. Then, the sample was placed in the instrumented hot press and squeezed. The squeezed sample was finally scanned to quantify all changes in the position, orientation and shape of the marker strands.

2.3.1 Sample pre-consolidation

The samples used in this study were cut from a 150 mm by 150 mm ROS flat panel pre-consolidated by compression moulding. The following sub-sections describe the layup process used to place the silver strands among the mat and the processing cycle used to manufacture the panel.

The first layer containing 8 markers was placed on the bottom of the tool at the position and orientation shown by Figure 5. For a 6.5 mm thick consolidated plate, 250g of strands were divided in five equal weight batches. The first batch was added on top of the markers. Extreme caution was taken to avoid moving the markers while the strands were randomly placed. The same procedure was repeated five times before a last set of markers was placed on the top. Overall, 48 markers were used (6 layers of 8 strands).

Next, the mould was placed into a Wabash 100 Tons hot press preheated to 395 °C. A thermocouple was placed into a small hole on the side of the mould to measure and monitor the plate temperature during the cycle. A pressure of 22 bars was then applied and maintained during 15 minutes. The mould was

then cooled down to 70 °C at an approximate rate of 12 °C/min and was removed from the press when the temperature felt below 70 °C. The panels were trimmed and four 50mm x 50mm samples were cut using a diamond saw, according to the sample configuration shown on Figure 5.

2.3.2 X-Ray tomography

The pre-consolidated samples were scanned using an XTek HMXST 225 computed tomography system in order to determine the initial position, orientation and shape of the painted strands. All the samples were scanned in the same conditions, using an acceleration tension of 50 kV and a current of 297 μA. CT Pro was used to reconstruct the samples geometry and ORS Visual to visualise and analyze the data.

2.3.3 Squeeze flow

Table I shows the test matrix used to perform the three tests described in this paper. The samples were squeezed at a constant load during 5 minutes until the thickness reached a constant value.

3 Modelling

3.1 Yield stress fluid

A visco-plastic behaviour with a yield stress τ_Y , previously used [9-10] to model the flow behaviour of concentrated suspensions of long fibres used in sheet moulding compounds was selected as a first approximation (Eq. 1). During flow, the deviatoric stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is a function of the strain rate tensor \boldsymbol{D} . The yield stress in shear τ_Y is linked to the fibre-fibre friction coefficient and η_0 and Λ are equivalent viscosity and characteristic time and n is the Carreau exponent of the viscous fluid model for the matrix.

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = [\tau_Y + \eta_0(1 + (\Lambda\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}})^2)^{(n-1)/2}]\boldsymbol{D} \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = \sqrt{2\boldsymbol{D}:\boldsymbol{D}}$ is the equivalent strain rate. The yield stress τ_Y is linked to the dry friction between the different strands [10]. A high yield stress results in a plug-like flow profile [6]. The expected flow profile of ROS is illustrated on Figure 6. It shows an un-yielded region, where the shear stress is lower than yield stress ($\tau < \tau_Y$) [13].

3.2 Flow model

Because of the high viscosity of the composite melt, the inertia and gravity terms can be neglected, such that the equilibrium is:

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0} \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the total stress tensor. Considering the material incompressibility:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (3)$$

(\mathbf{u} being the velocity), the pressure appears as an additional unknown where:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\tau} - p\mathbf{I} \quad (4)$$

From the problem symmetry, only a quarter of the domain shown on Figure 7 is considered. Besides symmetry boundary conditions, the edge of the domain is let free and a vertical displacement $\dot{h}/2$ is applied on the boundary in contact with the platen. The platen velocity \dot{h} is an additional scalar unknown that is associated with the platen force balance equation:

$$\int_{\text{up}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{e}_y \cdot \mathbf{e}_y dS = \frac{F}{2} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{e}_y is the vertical normal vector to the boundary in contact with the platen. F is the closing force applied on the platen.

3.3 Implementation

The Stokes flow defined by equations (2), (3) and (4) was solved using the finite element method in COMSOL Multiphysics. An Eulerian approach with a fixed meshed geometry was considered and the problem was solved for steady state. A mixed formulation was pertained for the velocity and pressure fields using the built-in creeping flow module. The nonlinearity arising from the non constant viscosity (1) was handled with the COMSOL built-in lumped Newton-Raphson solver.

Instead of the conditional visco-plastic behaviour, the smoothed exponential approach suggested by Papanastasiou [14] and used later [13] was assumed here:

$$\eta_{eq} = \eta_0 \left(1 + (\Lambda \dot{\gamma})^2\right)^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}} + \frac{\tau_Y(1-e^{-m\dot{\gamma}})}{\dot{\gamma}} \quad (6)$$

The force balance (5) was implemented using an additional physics (global algebraic equation), thus adding the unknown \dot{h} to the model.

The parameters used in the model are given in Table 2. The viscous parameters η_0 , Λ and n , were adapted from previous work [1]. The yield stress τ_Y was fitted as explained hereunder (Section 4.3).

3.4 Parametric approach

As a first step, instead of solving for the complex transient, geometry change, a parametric approach was used. It consisted in solving the steady state problem for different geometries. The geometry was always rectangular but the height and width varied, ensuring a constant volume, according to the experiment. The model was solved for each of these geometries giving an insight of the flow at successive stages of squeezing.

4. Results and discussion

In this section, the modelling and experimental results obtained following the test procedure are presented and discussed.

4.1 Pre-consolidated samples micro-CT scans

Figure 8 shows the computed tomography results of a pre-consolidated sample prior to squeeze flow. Fig. 8a) shows a cross-sectional view of one row of markers, in the longitudinal direction and Fig. 8b) shows the markers in the perpendicular direction. Many features can be observed and quantified on those computed tomography results:

The heterogeneous distribution of strands in the part led to a compaction gradient. This was observed in all the pre-consolidated samples, where the top and bottom strands (near the tool surface) did not experience out-of-plane deformation, while the middle strands were bent. The markers remained mostly in the location where they were initially placed during the layup process.

Those observations were consistent with the deformation mechanisms identified in Section 1. The out-of-plane deformation observed on the markers in the middle of the sample was associated with the packing stress at low loads.

Moreover, the width of the markers after pre-consolidation ranged from 6.35 to 20mm, which is a 0 to 320% increase from the initial width (6.35mm). These large deformations at the mesoscopic scale contributed to the *inter-strand void content reduction*.

4.2 Post-processing micro-CT scans

Figure 9 shows a cross-sectional view of sample A before and after the squeeze flow test. The top and bottom markers remained at their initial position, showing that no slip occurred at the platen/material interface. On the other hand, the middle layer was subjected to a large in-plane deformation caused by inter-ply slippage between strands.

Figure 10 shows the profile of the measured in-plane displacement for samples A, B and C. The values were all measured in the middle of the strands, perpendicularly to the fibre direction. One can note that the displacement profiles were not symmetric. This is due to the heterogeneous distribution of strands in the parts.

This random factor led to local variability in the flow. In fact, the maximum in-plane displacement measured was 22mm on both sample A and B for markers located in the middle of the sample (markers 3 and 4). Moreover, all markers located in the middle of sample B flew in the same direction, while the other two samples had flow profile in both direction. Finally, it shows that locally the random factor has a stronger effect on the direction and magnitude of the flow front compared to the applied load.

4.3 Flow simulation

The velocity \mathbf{u} and strain rate $\dot{\gamma}$ are plotted on Fig. 11 for the maximum force (2225 N) and the initial geometry (6.5mm X 50.8 mm). At this stage the platen velocity is 59 $\mu\text{m/s}$. This order of magnitude was in agreement with the duration of the squeeze flow (few minutes to reduce from 6.5 to 3 mm.).

As shown on Fig. 11, the horizontal velocity profile was close to parabolic. This is in agreement with the strands displacement observed on the X-Ray tomography (Fig. 10). One should finally notice that the strain rate in the upper left corner approaches 0, in agreement with the expected un-yielded zone shown in Fig. 7 and predicted in the literature [13].

Fig. 12 shows the predicted platen velocity for reducing plate thickness. Three plots, corresponding to the three closing forces used experimentally are shown. The first curve shows that the highest closing forces results in the fastest mould velocity at initial thickness 6.5 mm. For a thinner plate, the closing velocity reduces to 0. A minimum thickness h_{∞} is observed for each force under which no flow occurs (the force is not enough to reach the yield stress and ensure flow). Indeed, the yield stress τ_Y strongly influences this minimum thickness h_{∞} and was therefore fitted using the experimentally measured final thicknesses that are given in table I. A yield stress value $\tau_Y = 10^4$ Pa was obtained.

5 Conclusions

Compression moulding of randomly oriented composite strands (ROS) is a process that would allow to rapidly form complex small parts, with final properties better than short fibres reinforced polymer injected moulded parts. During this forming process the motion of strands, linked to the macroscopic squeeze flow behaviour, is critical to ensure a good filling of the cavity. In this paper we investigated this macroscopic squeeze flow using experimental and modelling methods.

A novel technique was developed to track the strands motion, using X-Ray tomography. A conductive silver paint was applied on marker strands placed at key locations in the ROS mat. Tracing the strand positions before and after processing with X-Ray tomography, gave an insight on the deformation that the material experienced. It was found that the material does not slip along the mould platen. Moreover, each markers located in the middle of the samples expected random in-plane displacements and spread differently.

It was found that the heterogeneity of this novel material added a random component in the flow pattern. It has local effects on the direction and magnitude of the strands displacement and spreading. Therefore, the applied load cannot be directly used to locally predict the ROS flow front. Those phenomena would have been hard to predict without the use of markers.

In addition, in order to predict the squeeze flow, a model using visco-plastic behaviour was developed.

Modelling results were globally in agreement with the observed displacement profile and showed that a minimum thickness is eventually reached. The model can be used to predict the effect of the applied pressure and yield stress (related to the friction between strands) on the squeeze flow and the final thickness.

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Table I - Experimental test matrix

Sample	Processing temperature (°C)	Applied Load (N)	Final thickness (mm)
A	385	562.5	3.00
B	385	1125	3.75
C	385	2250	4.53

Table II – Parameters used in the simulation

m	1000s
τ_Y	1e4 Pa
η_0	2.5e6 Pa.s
n	0.65
Λ	50s

Fig.1. Randomly oriented strands ready to be processed in a flat plate.

Fig.2. Marker strands are used to trace the flow front.

Fig.3. Instrumented hot press.

Fig.4. Experimental procedure.

Fig. 5. Layup configuration. Marker strands are all placed in the same orientation and position through thickness.

Fig.6. Material is modeled as a yield stress fluid to represent the squeeze flow behaviour of ROS.

Fig.7. Domain and Boundary conditions. Imposed velocity on top, symmetry on left and bottom.

Fig.8. Computed tomography showing a pre-consolidated sample before squeeze flow a) longitudinal direction b) perpendicular direction.

Fig.9. Computed tomography a) before squeeze flow b) after squeeze flow.

Fig. 10. Measured in-plane displacement profile.

Fig. 11. Velocity and strain rate field for the initial thickness and a closing force $F=2225$ N. Only one quarter of the sample was modeled.

Fig.12. Predicted mould velocity versus plate thickness for the three closing forces

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